

Supporting Information: Individual Decision-Making in Coupled Agent-Environment Systems

Victoria Peterson^{1*}, Shania Sinha^{1*},
Karolina Chlopicka^{1*}, Henry Zwart^{1*}, and Debraj Roy¹

Faculty of Science, Informatics Institute, University of Amsterdam, Science Park 904, 1090 XH,
Amsterdam, The Netherlands.

{victoria.peterson, shania.sinha}@student.uva.nl,
{karolina.chlopicka, henry.zwart}@student.uva.nl,
d.roy@uva.nl

A Theory supplement: Schematic Representation

The flowchart in Figure 1 traces a single timestep for one agent. The agent receives two streams of input: from its local environment (personal environmental condition, which shapes the likelihood of taking positive or negative action) and from its neighborhood (memories of neighbors' past actions within radius, used to predict future neighborhood behavior and compute a peer pressure term). These inputs jointly determine the utility of taking a positive or negative environmental action, which is combined with the utility cost of deviating from the predicted neighborhood action into a final action utility. A logit function then converts this into a probability, from which the agent samples either a climate-friendly (+1) or degradative (-1) action. This action feeds back into both the environment and the neighbors' states, closing the loop for the next timestep.

B Methods supplement: ODD+D Implementation Details

B.1 Overview

Purpose and Entities The model explores how individual decisions to adopt environmental behaviors are shaped by environmental feedback and social norms, where agents are arranged on a 2-D grid and repeatedly choose between positive and negative environmental actions. Each agent has an adaptive behavioral preference, observes a local environmental state, and is influenced by their prediction of neighbors' past actions.

Process and scheduling Simulations run in discrete time-steps that each follow these specific steps:

1. *Environment Update*: Agents' environments evolve based on prior actions, using a user-definable function.

* Equal contribution.

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the interactions between an agent, its neighbors and its environment in a single timestep.

2. *Behavioral Adaptation:* Agents update their weight placed on positive or negative action in response to environmental conditions. Willingness to take positive action changes more strongly when the environment is neither fully degraded nor fully healthy.
3. *Prediction of Neighbors' Actions:* When enabled, agents estimate future neighbor behavior using linear or logistic prediction and a specified amount of memory of neighbor actions.
4. *Decision:* Agents select actions probabilistically based on their updated willingness to take positive or negative action and predicted social norms, as defined in the logit equation.

B.2 Design concepts

Theoretical Basis and Decision Making The model builds on theories of bounded rationality and norm-driven behavior, making decisions using a probabilistic logit model based on each agent's support and the predicted behavior of their neighbors.

Agent Learning, Sensing, and Predicting Agents sense their environment and recent neighbor actions, adjusting their tendency for action depending on environmental quality, taking more positive action in moderately degraded settings and less at environmental extremes. Agents also sense their neighbors' actions and retain a specified memory of those actions to predict overall neighborhood behavior using recent trends.

Interaction Agents interact with each other in a Moore neighborhood. The neighbors' actions are taken into consideration when an agent is trying to maximize its expected utility. An agent also directly interacts with the environment in its assigned location on the lattice by choosing an action that is dependent on the current state of the environment.

Collectives All agents are part of a neighborhood, and the action level of the neighborhood affects the environmental state of a given cell. Clusters of healthy or degraded environment form as a result of agent interaction with its neighbors and its environment. Cluster formation is an emergent property of the model.

Heterogeneity Each agent in the model has an independent preference for climate action. An agent also adapts its behaviour dependent on the state of the environment at its position in the lattice. In experiments with heterogeneous social influence, each agent's peer-pressure coefficient is initialized by sampling independently from a Uniform(0, 1) distribution, thereby seeding behavioral diversity.

Stochasticity Stochasticity in the model is introduced primarily through agents' action choices, which are drawn at each time step from a logit (softmax) distribution over their computed utilities. All results are obtained via multiple Monte Carlo replicates, each with a fresh random seed, to ensure that observed patterns reflect the variability induced by these stochastic processes.

Observation Time-series data for the environmental state and agent action is collected for many different parameter sets to analyze model behaviour. Some of the recorded metrics are: mean environment and action, pluralistic ignorance, spatial cluster counts and size distributions, and oscillation characteristics via Fourier analysis. These measurements are used to validate the observed model dynamics with theoretical expectations.

B.3 Details

Implementation and Initialization The model is implemented as both an object-oriented and vectorized agent-based simulation in Python, using a 2-D spatial grid where each cell represents a single agent who continuously chooses between improving or impairing their environment. The object-oriented model emphasizes modularity and ease-of-use, while the vector-based model emphasizes efficiency for large-scale experimentation — the vectorized model contains all of the most recent changes, so focus will be placed on that.

As opposed to the object-oriented method, the vectorized model encodes agents as rows in a structured array instead of as individual objects, where each array stores one attribute of the individual agent across multiple time steps, including actions, environmental states, or parameter values. This structure allows for vectorized operations, in which entire populations are updated in a single step using high-performance libraries like NumPy and SciPy.

Data Input The model does not use input data from external sources.

Sub-models

1. *Environmental Update Dynamics*: Either linear or piecewise exponential.
2. *Environmental Action Dynamics*: Driven by nonlinear response to environmental quality.
3. *Local Action Prediction*: Predict neighbor actions using linear or logistic regression.
4. *Decision Model*: Logit-based decision making between positive and negative action.

Experiments Systematic experiments were conducted on every combination of the parameters specified in the main paper and plotting γ_s and λ on heatmaps of different output values, including mean environmental status, number and size of clusters, and Fourier analysis of cyclic behaviors.

General behavior of the system was identified with the heatmaps and then isolated into slices of specific continuous parameter values to find the steepest critical point for qualitative phase transitions. Using the specific parameter value identified at the critical point, plots of model outcomes over-time were created to observe behavior before, after, and at the critical point. These results can then be compared to the mean-field approximation to observe differences caused by the model implementation.

C Results supplement: Sensitivity Analysis

When the model has multiple parameters, the sensitivity analysis is key to distinguishing influential parameters from the ones that don't significantly impact the model's behavior. This, in turn, can be used to simplify the model by removing such parameters. Additionally, sensitivity analysis can help identify critical or otherwise interesting regions in the space of the input factors. A suitable sensitivity analysis must be chosen with careful attention to the characteristics of the model output. Failing to do so can undermine the reliability of the results.

As model input, we chose to investigate the following parameters: Grid length, rationality (λ), memory size, adaptation rate (γ_s), neighborhood radius, and environment recovery rate (β_n^+). The range of values used for parameter sampling is presented in Table 1.

Following the procedure for global sensitivity analysis parameter space was sampled, and model simulation was performed in order to gather output statistics. Samples were generated using Saltelli's extension of the Sobol sequence (as implemented in the SALib

Parameter	Min. value	Max. value	Type
Grid length	5	50	integer
Rationality	0	10	float
Memory size	2	10	integer
Adaptation rate	0.001	0.05	float
Neighborhood radius	0	1	integer
Recovery rate	0.5	2	float

Table 1: Range of parameter values used in the PAWN sensitivity analysis.

Python package). For our simulation, the number of samples was set to $N = 2048$ and the number of parameters $D = 6$. This results in $N(D + 2)$ simulations [3]. Models were re-run 5 times for each parameter set, with different random seeds to account for stochasticity, for a total of 81920 simulations:

$$(2048 \cdot (6 + 2)) \cdot 5 = 81920$$

We chose 6 measures of the model output:

- *Mean environment* - average state of the environment at the final time step, computed over all cells of the 2-D lattice.
- *Mean action* - average agent’s action at the final time step, computed over all cells of the 2-D lattice.
- *Pluralistic ignorance* - capturing how much an agent’s behavior is distorted due to the misperception of social norms.
- *Cluster count* - number of healthy environment clusters at the final time step. Cell was considered healthy if the mean value of the environment was above 0.6.
- *Peak frequency* - the frequency at which oscillations have the highest average power within its full-width.
- *Dominant frequency power* - measure of the oscillation mode with the largest magnitude or impact on system stability.

To ensure measurements are taken at system equilibrium, we run each model for 2000 time steps, which our testing shows to be sufficient in most cases.

The empirical distributions of the output metrics are shown in Figure 2. These types of distributions are not suitable for variance-based sensitivity methods because such methods rely on variance being a meaningful measure of output uncertainty. However, this assumption does not hold for multi-modal or highly skewed distributions. For this reason, we chose to use the PAWN method for our sensitivity analysis. Unlike variance-based approaches, PAWN is a density-based method that can be applied effectively to all types of output distributions, including those that are highly skewed or multi-modal [2].

The results of the PAWN sensitivity analysis are shown in Fig. 3a. Each row corresponds to an output metric of the model, while each column represents one of the input parameters. The values in the heatmap indicate the importance of each parameter for the corresponding output.

Fig. 2: Empirical output distributions as observed across all samples

Several clear patterns emerge. Mean environment and peak frequency are most influenced by memory size. Mean action is primarily affected by recovery rate, and the same is true for Pluralistic ignorance. Cluster count and dominant frequency power are most influenced by adaptation rate.

Neighborhood radius has minimal influence on any of the selected output metrics, indicating that vision structure has limited impact on the system’s overall behavior. This may be due to only two possible vision radii implemented in the model: the Moore neighborhood of an agent or the full grid. The grid length also shows low sensitivity across most outputs, further suggesting that the spatial structure of the grid plays a relatively minor role compared to other parameters.

D Appendix: Mean Field model derivations

D.1 Expected agent action

Consider the action probability as defined in Equation 1.

$$\mathbb{P}(a_i^t = a) = \frac{\exp(\lambda V_i(a))}{\exp(\lambda V_i(C)) + \exp(\lambda V_i(D))} \quad (1)$$

By expanding the representative utility and simplifying, we can eliminate any terms not dependent on a (the specific action). For clarity, we omit the t superscripts on a_i^t

(a) PAWN sensitivity indices

(b) Sobol sensitivity indices

Fig. 3: Sensitivity indices computed with PAWN (left) and Sobol (right).

and s_i^t :

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i(a) &= (1 - w_i)[2 + (s_i - 2)a] - w(a - \bar{a}_i)^2 \\
 &= (1 - w_i)(2 + s_i a - 2a) - w(1 - 2a\bar{a}_i + \bar{a}_i^2) \\
 &= [2(1 - w_i) - w(1 + \bar{a}_i^2)] \\
 &\quad + a[(1 - w_i)(s_i - 2) + 2w\bar{a}_i]
 \end{aligned}$$

Taking $z_i = (1 - w_i)(s_i - 2) + 2w\bar{a}_i$, we derive agent i 's expected action:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbb{E}[a_i] &= \mathbb{P}(a_i = C) - \mathbb{P}(a_i = D) \\
 &= \frac{\exp(\lambda z_i) - \exp(-\lambda z_i)}{\exp(\lambda z_i) + \exp(-\lambda z_i)} \\
 &= \tanh(\lambda(1 - w_i)(s_i - 2) + 2\lambda w\bar{a}_i)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

D.2 Expected mean action

To obtain an expression for the population-level expected action, we first make the following simplifying assumptions:

1. The heterogeneous w_i attributes assume their expected value, $w_i = w$.
2. Agents' adapt sufficiently fast, such that their action probability, and thus action preferences, are stationary.
3. For any pair of agents, their action probabilities are independent (the mean-field assumption).

Taken together, these assumptions imply that $\bar{a}_i = m$ for each agent $i \in N$, where m is the population-level expected action, and $w_i = w$, $s_i = s$. Thus, the expected mean action is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 m &= \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k a_i \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{k} (\mathbb{E}[a_1] + \dots + \mathbb{E}[a_k]) \\
 &= \frac{1}{k} \cdot k \cdot \mathbb{E}[a_i] \\
 &= \tanh(\lambda(1-w)(s-2) + 2\lambda w m)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The fixed-point equation is illustrated with varying w , λ , s in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Graphical solutions (fixed points) of the average action mean-field equation for two levels of initial support for cooperation (top) $s = 2.0$ and (bottom) $s = 3.0$ for varying levels of social-norm coefficient (w) and rationality (λ).

Equation 3 has between 1 and 3 solutions. We now characterize the necessary and sufficient conditions for three solutions to exist. Rewriting Equation 3 as a fixed-point problem $f(m)$,

$$\begin{aligned} f(m) &= g(m) - m \\ g(m) &= \tanh(\lambda(1-w)(s-2) + 2\lambda w m) \end{aligned}$$

we observe that $f(m) = 0$ can have three solutions, only if $g'(m) > 1$ for some $m \in [-1, 1]$. This condition is satisfied when:

$$1 < g'(m) = \operatorname{sech}^2(\lambda z) \cdot 2\lambda w \leq 2\lambda w$$

Thus for three solutions to exist, it is necessary that $\frac{1}{2\lambda w} < 1$, i.e., individual rationality and the influence of social norms must be sufficiently high. Now observe that for multiple solutions to exist, it is sufficient to show that:

1. f has two turning points within the domain $m \in [-1, 1]$, and that
2. These correspond to expected actions m_1^*, m_2^* which lie below and above the diagonal, respectively.

With $f'(m) = 2\lambda w \cdot \operatorname{sech}^2(\lambda z) - 1$, the turning points are given by:

$$m^* = -\frac{(1-w)(s-2)}{2w} \pm \frac{1}{2\lambda w} \operatorname{arccosh}(\sqrt{2\lambda w})$$

D.3 Mean-field dynamics

We derive the temporal dynamics of m by taking the time derivative of Equation 3:

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = \frac{(1-w)\lambda \operatorname{sech}^2(\lambda z)}{1 - 2\lambda w \operatorname{sech}^2(\lambda z)} \cdot \frac{ds}{dt} \quad (4)$$

Where the mean-field $\frac{ds}{dt}$ is defined by:

$$\frac{1}{\gamma_s} \frac{ds}{dt} = \beta_s^+ \cdot \sigma(n)(4-s) - \beta_s^- \cdot (1-\sigma(n))s$$

Observe that as the denominator in Equation 4 approaches 0, the derivative diverges. This occurs precisely at the identified turning points of the fixed-point function f . Thus when $\frac{1}{2\lambda w} < 1$, the mean-field model predicts increasing attraction to the two stable fixed points as they are approached.

Equilibria in the mean-field dynamical system are characterized by mean environment n^* and action m^* such that $\frac{dn}{dt} = \frac{dm}{dt} = 0$. The temporal environment derivative in the mean-field model is given by:

$$\frac{1}{\gamma_n} \frac{dn}{dt} = \beta_n^+ \cdot (1-n)\mathbb{P}(C) - \beta_n^- \cdot n\mathbb{P}(D)$$

Thus the environment is stationary when:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \beta_n^+ \cdot (1 - n) - \beta_n^- \cdot n_i^t (1 - \alpha_i^t) \\ \implies n^* &= \frac{\beta_n^+ \mathbb{P}(C)}{\beta_n^+ \mathbb{P}(C) + \beta_n^- \mathbb{P}(D)} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

From Equation 4, the expected action is stationary when:

$$(1 - w)\lambda \operatorname{sech}^2(\lambda z) \cdot \frac{ds}{dt} = 0$$

Since $\operatorname{sech} > 0$, we find that $\frac{dm}{dt} = 0$ when agents are unaffected by peer pressure, are completely irrational, or when the mean action preference is unchanging. The latter condition holds when:

$$s^* = \frac{4 \cdot \beta_s^+ \sigma(n)}{\beta_s^+ \sigma(n) + \beta_s^- (1 - \sigma(n))} \quad (6)$$

Now suppose that n^* is such that $\frac{dn}{dt} = 0$. Solving for the corresponding $P_C^* = \mathbb{P}(C)$, we find:

$$P_C^* = \frac{\beta_n^- n^*}{\beta_n^- n^* + \beta_n^+ (1 - n^*)}$$

However, from the logit model definition, we also have that:

$$\begin{aligned} P_C^* &= \frac{\exp(\lambda z)}{\exp(\lambda z) + \exp(-\lambda z)} \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-2\lambda z)} \end{aligned}$$

Thus we can rearrange for the corresponding steady-state action preference, s^* :

$$\begin{aligned} P_C^* &= \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-2\lambda z)} \\ \frac{1}{P_C^*} &= 1 + \exp(-2\lambda z) \\ -\frac{1}{2\lambda} \ln \left(\frac{1 - P_C^*}{P_C^*} \right) &= (1 - w)(s^* - 2) + 2w \cdot \overbrace{m}^{2P_C^* - 1} \\ s^* &= \frac{1}{1 - w} \left[2(1 - 2wP_C^*) - \frac{1}{2\lambda} \ln \left(\frac{1 - P_C^*}{P_C^*} \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Since P_C^* depends on n^* , by equating Equations 6 and 7, we obtain a fixed-point problem, whose numerical solution defines the system equilibria (n^*, s^*) . Finally, we recover the equilibrium expected action as

$$m^* = P_C^* - P_D^* = 2P_C^* - 1$$

Example dynamics are illustrated for varying parameters in Figure 5, with red circles identifying the equilibria, and the $\frac{dn}{dt} = 0$ nullcline depicted with a grey dashed line.

Fig. 5: Phase portraits of the mean field dynamics of our model for varying social-norm coefficient (w) and rationality level of agents (λ).

E Appendix: Power Law Fitting

To determine whether certain quantities in the simulation follow a power-law distribution, we fit empirical distributions using the `powerlaw` Python package [1].

Power Law Model

A continuous power-law distribution is defined by the probability density function:

$$p(x) = Cx^{-\alpha}, \quad x \geq x_{\min}, \quad (8)$$

where $\alpha > 1$ is the scaling exponent, x_{\min} is the lower bound above which the power-law behavior holds, and C is a normalization constant.

Given a set of n observations $\{x_i\}$ such that $x_i \geq x_{\min}$, the scaling exponent α is estimated via the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE):

$$\alpha = 1 + n \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \ln \left(\frac{x_i}{x_{\min}} \right) \right]^{-1}. \quad (9)$$

Determining x_{\min}

To find the optimal value of x_{\min} , the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) distance between the cumulative distribution function (CDF) and the fitted power-law model is computed for

a range of x_{\min} . The value that minimizes this distance is selected:

$$x_{\min} = \arg \min_x \sup_{x \geq x_{\min}} |S(x) - P(x)|, \quad (10)$$

where $S(x)$ is the empirical CDF and $P(x)$ is the CDF of the fitted model.

Goodness-of-Fit Test and p -Value

To assess the power-law fit, a goodness-of-fit test is done by simulating the fitted model and computing their KS distances from the model. The p -value is then calculated as the fraction of these simulated distances that exceed the empirical KS distance:

$$p = \frac{\# \text{ simulations with } D_{\text{sim}} > D_{\text{emp}}}{\# \text{ simulations}}. \quad (11)$$

A p -value greater than 0.1 is generally taken to indicate that the power-law hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Model Comparison

To further validate the fit, we compute the log-likelihood ratio R between the power-law model and an alternative distribution (e.g., exponential). The corresponding p -value is calculated to determine if the observed difference is statistically significant:

$$R = \log \left(\frac{L_{\text{power law}}}{L_{\text{alternative}}} \right). \quad (12)$$

A positive R indicates that the data are more likely under the power-law model.

References

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